

Geochemistry of the Basaltic Lava flows of the Malwa Plateau region: A Case study of Indore area (M.P.) India.

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Abstract

The basic volcanic rocks around Indore belong to Deccan trap volcanic activity and constitute the central part of Malwa Plateau. The area occupied by seven basaltic lava flows along with inter-trappeans and red bole/red clay bands. The plot of Mafic and Felsic Index indicate that magmatic differentiation process has been operative during the course of origin of these rocks. Al_2O_3 -MgO variation diagram for these basalts correspond to iron rich tholeiitic basaltic rocks. Jensen (1976) also confirms the same iron rich tholeiitic nature of these rocks. The values of MgO-FeO- Al_2O_3 plotted on the diagram reveal the basic rocks of the study area belongs to continental basalt tectonic environment. Calculated values of Mg# in the range between 22.17 to 35.35 with an average value of 26.32 also confirms the high degree of fractional crystallization of the basaltic magma. These basaltic rocks show a higher trace element concentration of vanadium and chromium with an average of 431.67 and 185.63 ppm respectively. These values of vanadium are close to the values of Quartz-normative tholeiites and the value of chromium suggest that it is camouflaged in pyroxene and fractionation in ferromagnesian minerals led to iron enrichment. Concentration of Sr in the present rocks is agreeable with that of tholeiitic basalts. Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y ratios of the basaltic rocks, which also attributed to the low to moderate degree of partial melting of mantle where as variation in the concentration of Zr and REE explain the crustal assimilation. Average Y, La-Lu values are close to the values of tholeiitic basaltic rocks from continents.

Introduction

The area around Indore represents a part of Malwa Plateau region covering the western part of Madhya Pradesh. It is occupied mainly by the basaltic lava flows of the Deccan Trap igneous activity. The area of present study is bounded by Latitude 22°35' to 22°50' N and Longitude 75°50' to 76°0' E and falls on the Survey of India Toposheet No. 46 N/13 and 46 N/14 covering a total area of about 460 km² of Indore district of Madhya Pradesh.

Methodology

The chemical analysis of 07 representative rock samples of the lava flows have been carried out for their major, trace and REE using ICMS at Geochemical Laboratory, NGRI, Hyderabad. Collected rock samples were chosen for the chemical analysis, after cleaning samples to remove weathered surface oven dried and powdered up to -200 mesh size. For dissolution savillex pressure decomposition vessels (60ml.) (Savillex Corporation, Minnoetnka, Mn, USA) were

used. Electronic grade Hydrofluoric Acid, AR grade HClO_4 , distilled HNO_3 and HCl and lithium metaborate were used for the preparation of samples. The various graphical techniques and discriminatory plots as proposed by different workers from time to time were used for interpreting the chemical data to evaluate the of petrogenesis of Deccan trap volcanism.

Geology

The geological map (Fig.1) of the study area has been prepared using Survey of India Toposheet No. 46 N/13 and 46 N/14. The lava flows of the study area shows, step like terraces and flat topped hills which are very common in the region to gather with Messa, Butte and other features based on criteria laid down. Seven lava flows have been delineated. Columnar jointing is very common in the area and it is observed at various localities in the study area (Field photo 2A and B).

The lava flows of the area reported variety of secondary minerals like Zeolites, varieties of silica and calcite. These secondary minerals are filled in the vesicles, generally at the top of the lava flows. Zeolites and allied minerals Heulandite, Stibnite, Mesolite, Laumonite, Chabasite, Appophyllite have also been reported.

Fig. 1. Location and Geological map of the study area.

Fig. 2A. Field Photograph showing Columnar jointing in the basaltic rocks, IIIrd flow of the study area, at Bhuritekri.

Fig. 2B. Field Photograph showing Columnar jointing in the IIIrd flow of the study area, at Bhuritekri.

Geochemistry

The chemical analysis of the seven lava flows of Malwa plateau region are analyzed for major, trace and REE and given in Table 1 along with their normative values. A comparative study of

chemical parameters and oxide ratios of standard basaltic rocks from different parts of India and world along with the Indore flows are being presented for direct comparison. Chemical parameters and oxide ratios have been incorporated. These chemical parameters and oxide ratios are useful for chemical classification and understanding the chemical characters of the rocks and their evolution.

It is observed that, these basaltic rocks have practically a constant chemical composition. Average and ranges of the various oxides as mentioned in the Table 1. The value of various oxides has been estimated for the lava flows of study area which reveals that the maximum variation of 4.85% is shown in SiO_2 and the minimum variation of 0.08% is shown by P_2O_5 . The analyses agree fairly well with the average of Deccan basalt (Sukeshwala and Poldervart, 1958). The high Fe_2O_3 indicates iron enrichment probably due to the oxidation of opaque minerals in the groundmass. The low TiO_2 is very characteristic, which indicates poor presence of ilmenite. The low K_2O in the lava flows of the area in comparison to the rocks of the other region is remarkable. Lava flows of the study area have been classified using TAS diagram (Fig.3) after LeBas et al.

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Fig. 3. TAS diagram after LeBas et al., 1986.

Another discrimination diagram between Na_2O vs K_2O were also plotted all the samples of the study area fall in the sodic series (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Discrimination diagram Na_2O vs K_2O (after, La Maitre R., 2002).

Variation diagram (Fig. 4) plot after Viljoen et al. (1982) for the basaltic rocks of the study area reveals that all the plots lie in the 'C' field of the diagram, which represents the Iron rich tholeiitic nature of the rocks. It may, therefore be concluded that an iron enrichment trend in the basaltic rocks of the study area is predominant.

Fig. 5. Al_2O_3 vs MgO diagram (after Viljoen et al., 1982)

Ewart (1982) and Le Maitre (1989) diagram (Fig. 6) for the basaltic rocks of the study area also confirm the nomenclature of these as basalt and basaltic andesite.

Fig. 6. K_2O vs SiO_2 diagram for lava flows of the study area. Field boundaries and rock-suit labels from Le Maitre (1989) except shoshonitic from Ewart (1982).

The plotted data (Fig. 6) show a gradual progression of the cotectic line. This progression of the liqui

972) clearly indicate a agioclase field towards is documented by the

Fig. 7. Plots of Lava Flows of the study area in Di-Ab-An diagram (Kushiro, 1972) for 1 atm. dry condition.

FeO-MgO-($Na_2O + K_2O$) variation diagram Fig. 8 (Irvine and Baragar, 1971) indicates a distinct tholeiitic nature of the lava flows of the study area.

Fig. 8. Plot of FeO-MgO ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}+\text{K}_2\text{O}$) triangular diagram dividing line is after Irvine and Baragar, 1971).

To understand the nature of basaltic lava flows of the study area, the results of chemical analyses plotted on the $\text{FeO} + \text{TiO}_2 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{MgO}$ diagram (Fig. 9) after Jensen (1976). Plotted data also confirms a high - iron rich lepicited earlier also in Fig. 4 and 7.

Fig. 9. Plots of Lava Flows of the study area in $\text{FeO}+\text{TiO}_2-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3-\text{MgO}$ in Jensen's (1976) diagram.

To understand the tectonic setting of the basalts of the study area, the $\text{MgO}-\text{FeO}-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ diagram (Fig. 10) has been used to discriminate amongst the Ocean Island Basalts, Continental Basalts, Ocean Flows Basalts, Volcanic Arc Basalts and Spreading Centres Basalts. The values of $\text{MgO}-\text{FeO}-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ for the lava flows of the area have been plotted in the above mentioned diagram, which indicate that basic rocks of study area fall within the continental basalt field. It is

therefore, clear that the basaltic rocks of the present area belong to continental basalt tectonic environment.

Fig. 10. FeO-MgO-Al₂O₃ discriminant diagram (after, Pearce et al., 1977).

To understand the process of fractional crystallization of the lava flows La vs La/Yb diagram (Fig. 11) is plotted for the samples of the study area. The study reveals that the parts of lava flows falls between the line of partial melting and fraction crystallization indicating that the trace elements of the lava flows were controlled by both processes during the evolution of the lava flows.

Fig. 11. La-La/Yb plot for the rocks of the present area (after, Moradi et al., 2022).

To understand the processes of fractional crystallization and partial melting during the magmatic evolution Harker's variation plots (Fig. 12) were plotted. This diagram show correlation between major elements concentration of the lava flows. The Fe₂O₃ and TiO₂ show negative correlation with MgO. Whereas the positive correlation of CaO with MgO suggests the presence of clinopyroxene fractionation. This correlation show that basaltic andesite is a product of basalt fractional crystallization. The negative correlation between SiO₂, Al₂O₃ with MgO indicate that accumulation of clinopyroxene. The Fe₂O₃/FeO ratio of the lava flows of the study area in all seven lava flows is 0.25 which is consistent in all flows of the area. It is higher than the normal

values. The low value of this ratio signifies the reduced oxidation condition at the time of

1.

Fig. 12. Harker variation diagram for major oxides of the lava flows of the study area.

Trace and Rare-Earth Elements

The concentration range, average and ratios of various trace and rare earth elements in the representative rock samples of each flow have been shown in Table 2 and 3 respectively. In the basaltic rocks of the study area the concentration of Co ranges between 19.90 - 74.08 ppm with an average value of 61.29 ppm. Goldschmidt (1962) has reported Co concentration of 80 ppm in basaltic rocks which is slightly higher than the value of basalts of the study area.

Co enters the same minerals as Ni but in lesser extent with more consistent value. Olivine, pyroxenes, amphiboles and titanomagnetites are the carriers of Co. The amount of Co shows a gradual change with differentiation in basaltic rocks. In the basaltic rocks of the study area the concentration of Ni ranges between 39.12-253.68 ppm with an average value of 118.01 ppm.

The value of Zn in present study varies between 93.09 ppm and 258.04 ppm with an average value of 179.74 ppm. Traces of Zn in olivine, pyroxene, plagioclase, amphiboles and Fe-oxides have been reported (Wadepohl, 1953). This indicates that higher concentration of Zn in the study area is due to the presence of Ferro magnesium minerals in greater proportion.

In the present study the value of Rb range is from 0.99 ppm - 40.40 ppm the average being 12.96 ppm. This value is agreeable with basaltic rocks as mentioned by (Faurey and Hurley, 1963). On the other hand Rb/Sr ratio for the present rocks is 0.049 ppm which is quit agreeable with value of olivine basalts this also indicate a deep origin (higher pressure).

The Sr content of basaltic rocks has been variously estimated as 461 ppm. Prinz, 1967 found that the Sr content varies widely between 18 to 2000 ppm with a medium of 400 ppm and an arithmetic mean of 544 ppm. The analysed value of Sr in the present rocks show a wide range from 105.39 ppm to 347.96 ppm. These values are agreeable with the values of tholeiitic basalts.

Vanadium is probably present in magmas as the V^{3+} ion. It is largely removed in magnetite, in which it proxies for Fe^{3+} ; its ionic radius is greater than ferric iron, but its electro-negativity is much less and its crystal field stabilization energy higher. In the basaltic lava flows of the study area the concentration of vanadium ranges from 126.56 ppm to 569.47 ppm with an average value of 431.67 ppm. These values are close to the values of Quartz-normative tholeiites.

The chromium concentration in the rocks of present area varies from 67.43 ppm to 597.77 ppm with an average value of 185.63 ppm. Prinz (1967) states Cr concentration range of 2-500 ppm in

tholeiitic and 5-500 ppm in alkalic basalts. The higher concentration of chromium in the rocks of the study area is mainly due to the presence of pyroxene and iron enrichment.

The value of the present study has a wide range from 59.49 ppm to 258.60 ppm with an average value of 200.43 ppm Zr is concentrated in pyroxene of basaltic rocks. Wilkinson (1958) p.143 and others find that Zr enters the early and middle stage pyroxenes and it increases in residual magma. It is also present in analcite and its content decreases with differentiation. Prinz, 1967 has given an arithmetic mean value of Zr 100 ppm in the basaltic rocks.

In basalts its presence is very significant and in the present study it is estimated in the ranges from 3.50 ppm to 18.87 ppm, the average being 13.08 ppm. The low concentration of Ni suggests the tholeiitic nature of the basaltic rocks of the study area.

In the present study the concentration of Ce ranges from 0.06 ppm to 1.03 ppm. The average being 0.28 ppm suggests the low concentration in basaltic rocks in comparison to earth's crust concentration i.e. 3 ppm.

Ba is found mainly in feldspar, feldspathoids and to a small extent in apatite K feldspars are richer in Ba (2000-3000 ppm) than coexisting plagioclase owing to the strong coherence of K and Ba. The low value of Ba in the basaltic rocks 18.97 ppm to 93.87 ppm of the study area suggests the tholeiitic nature of the rocks.

Y is found in soil concentrations between 10 and 150 ppm (dry weight average of 23 ppm) and in sea water at 9 ppt. Lunar rock samples collected during the American Apollo Project have a relatively high content of Y. The concentration of Y in the basaltic rocks of the area ranges between 17.70 ppm to 54.23 ppm with an average value of 44.30 ppm which is higher than average value of Earth's crust value (31 ppm). Ce concentration in the basaltic lava flows of the study area ranges from 11.86 ppm to 58.66 with an average value of 38.75 ppm. The higher concentration of Ce in the present case is agreeable with the views as expressed above.

The Yb concentration in the basaltic lava flows of the area ranges from 0.98 ppm to 3.03 ppm with an average value of 2.38 ppm. The average value of Yb of the area is the lower than the Earth crust value. The average concentration of Lu of basaltic rocks of the area is 0.52 ppm, which is very close to the abundance of Earth crust as mentioned above. The absolute abundances of Y and La-Lu have been determined for the basaltic lava flows of the study area and given in Table 4. Comparison of these values with Tholeiitic Basalts from Oceanic Islands and Continents, (Deccan plateau India); Tholeiitic Basalts from Oceanic Islands and Continents (Karoo, South Africa) Transitional Tholeiitic Basalts from Oceanic Ridges and from the

Continents (Mid-Atlantic Ridge) mentioned in Table 4. The average value of $\sum Y$, La-Lu ≈ 163.69 in the basaltic lava flows of the study area is very close to the value as given by Frey et al. (1964) $\sum Y$, La-Lu ≈ 147 for the tholeiitic basalts from continents.

Variations in Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y can be attributed to different degrees of partial melting of mantle. Variation in Zr, rare earth elements and Rb/Nb indicate fractional crystallization and significant coupled crustal assimilation away from the Deccan plume center. These ratios have been calculated for the basaltic lava flows of the study area and mentioned in the Table 6.2. Nb/Y ratios ranges from 0.19-1.37 with an average value of 0.28; Rb/Y ratios ranges from 0.095-0.82 with an average value of 0.26 and Ba/Zr ratios ranges from 0.24-0.49 with an average value of 0.31. This may be suggested that variation in Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y ratios of the basaltic lava flows of the area may be explained by low to moderate degree of partial melting of mantle, while the crustal assimilation can be explained by the variation of Zr and REE's.

Table 1. Major oxides of the Basaltic Lava Flows of the area with Normative Values (wt.%)

Constituents	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	Average	Range
SiO ₂	52.91	50.42	51.74	50.14	50.83	53.95	49.1	51.29	49.1-53.95
TiO ₂	1.89	2.35	2.01	1.51	1.58	0.79	2.21	1.83	0.79-2.71
Al ₂ O ₃	13.04	12.97	12.96	13.1	13.77	14.11	12.7	13.23	12.7-14.11
F ₂ O ₃	2.88	2.96	2.94	2.75	2.73	2.35	3.17	2.82	2.3 - 3.7
FeO	11.51	11.83	11.75	10.99	10.91	9.38	12.67	11.29	9.38 - 12.67
MnO	0.16	0.19	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.13	0.20	0.16	0.2-0.19
MgO	4.25	4.69	4.63	7.79	5.33	4.70	5.24	5.09	4.25- 7.79
CaO	8.71	9.83	9.40	10.36	10.39	10.02	9.82	9.79	9.4- 10.39
Na ₂ O	2.26	2.42	2.22	1.79	2.32	2.30	2.12	2.20	1.79- 2.42
K ₂ O	0.65	0.33	0.27	0.13	0.16	0.37	0.28	0.31	0.13- 0.65
P ₂ O ₅	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.17	0.25	0.22	0.19	0.21	0.17- 0.25
Total	98.47	98.21	98.29	98.87	98.42	98.34	98.20	98.40	98.20 - 98.87
Q	9.78	5.52	8.52	4.32	5.22	8.34	4.56	6.60	3.9-16.62
Or	3.89	2.24	2.22	0.55	1.11	2.22	1.66	1.98	0.55-19.46
ab	18.86	20.43	18.86	14.14	19.38	19.38	17.81	18.40	10.09-20.34
an	23.63	23.35	24.46	27.80	26.68	26.56	24.46	25.27	20.85-27.52
di	15.16	19.94	17.19	18.70	19.38	17.65	19.70	18.24	17.48-25.22
hy	18.53	17.43	18.82	26.01	19.09	19.58	20.15	19.94	7.5-24.7
ol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
mt	4.18	4.41	4.17	3.94	3.94	3.94	5.80	4.34	2.24-4.65
il	3.65	4.41	3.80	2.88	3.04	1.37	4.25	3.34	1.6-5.44
ap	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.33	0.67	0.67	0.33	0.57	0.33-1.33
Total	98.32	98.40	98.71	98.67	98.51	99.71	98.72	98.68	98.02 - 99.54

Table 2. Trace Elements Abundance in the Basaltic lava flows of the Indore area (in ppm)

Element	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	Range	Average
Sc	44.92	52.10	50.80	49.62	17.29	56.13	50.45	17.29 -56.13	45.90
V	413.60	540.77	534.44	441.59	126.56	345.32	569.47	126.56 - 569.47	431.67
Cr	96.52	131.44	126.05	597.77	67.43	147.96	132.29	67.43 - 597.77	185.63
Co	61.67	70.86	73.17	73.93	19.90	55.42	74.08	19.90 - 74.08	61.29
Ni	97.18	115.35	118.06	253.68	39.12	95.71	107.01	39.12 - 253.68	118.01
Cu	225.63	309.17	343.13	238.28	74.75	247.88	356.33	74.75 - 356.33	256.45
Zn	234.97	188.05	178.13	149.49	93.09	155.97	258.49	93.09 - 258.04	179.74
Ga	28.84	28.23	27.86	24.28	8.51	24.40	30.24	8.51 - 30.24	24.62
Rb	40.40	16.70	13.40	2.13	0.99	4.78	12.36	0.99 -40.40	12.96
Sr	347.96	295.42	291.74	249.65	105.39	197.67	343.63	105.39 - 347.96	261.63
Zr	298.60	253.26	243.94	156.66	59.49	174.17	256.90	59.49 - 258.60	200.43
Nb	15.19	17.98	17.13	9.09	3.50	9.85	18.87	3.50 - 18.87	13.08
Cs	1.03	0.29	0.24	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.23	0.06 - 1.03	0.28
Ba	93.87	67.24	59.68	45.45	18.97	85.84	74.52	18.97 - 93.87	63.93
Hf	6.17	6.19	5.85	3.82	1.42	4.25	6.19	1.42 - 6.19	4.84
Ta	1.05	0.93	1.35	0.70	0.34	0.75	1.40	0.34 - 1.43	0.93
Pb	2.64	2.25	2.74	2.59	1.60	2.30	1.93	1.60 - 2.74	2.29
Th	4.13	2.77	2.47	1.11	0.88	4.03	1.76	0.88 - 4.13	2.45
U	0.47	0.46	0.44	0.17	0.08	0.42	0.29	0.08 - 4.47	0.33
Y	49.14	52.12	50.38	36.39	17.70	50.26	54.23	17.70 - 54.23	44.30
Nb/Y	0.31	0.34	0.34	0.25	0.20	0.20	0.35	-	-
Rb/Y	0.82	0.32	0.27	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.23	-	-
Ba/Zr	0.31	0.27	0.24	0.29	0.32	0.49	0.29	-	-
Rb/Sr	0.12	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04	-	-

Table 3. Rare Earth Elements Abundance in the Basaltic lava flows of the Indore area (in ppm)

La	28.47	21.25	20.53	10.65	5.25	19.95	19.63	5.25 - 28.47	17.96
Ce	58.66	47.18	45.46	25.23	11.86	38.70	44.16	11.86 - 58.66	38.75
Pr	6.82	5.88	5.62	3.37	1.61	4.42	5.83	1.61 - 6.82	4.79
Nd	34.85	31.72	30.34	19.01	9.33	21.94	32.05	9.33 - 34.85	25.60
Sm	8.14	7.88	7.66	5.31	2.59	5.35	8.34	2.59 - 8.34	6.46
Eu	2.52	2.54	2.41	1.81	0.85	1.73	2.73	0.85 - 2.73	2.08
Gd	8.57	8.55	8.11	5.65	2.81	6.43	9.02	2.81 - 9.02	7.02
Tb	1.23	1.27	1.25	0.89	0.44	1.06	1.37	0.44 - 1.37	1.07
Dy	8.17	8.62	8.35	6.06	2.94	7.50	8.91	2.94 - 8.91	7.22
Ho	1.58	1.69	1.63	1.21	0.57	1.59	1.75	0.57 - 1.75	1.43
Er	4.10	4.34	4.13	3.00	1.44	4.39	4.51	1.44 - 4.51	3.70
Tm	0.46	0.49	0.45	0.34	0.17	0.51	0.50	0.17 - 0.51	0.41
Yb	2.54	2.73	2.67	1.90	0.98	3.03	2.86	0.98 - 3.03	2.38
Lu	0.57	0.60	0.59	0.42	0.20	0.67	0.62	0.20 - 0.67	0.52

Fig. 13. Nb/La vs Nb/Th diagram (after, Zhang et. al., 2011).

Fig. 14. Th vs Rb/La diagram (after, Taylor and McLennan, 1985).

Fig. 15. La/Nb vs Ce/Pb (after, Barry, 2003). Values of N-MORB, E-MORB, Primitive Mantle and OIB are from Sun and McDonough, uncontaminated basalt zone from Rooney et al., 2007. The value of Upper continental Crust and Lower Continental Crust from Wedepohl (1953).

The Th/Ta ratio of the lava flows varies between 1.3 to 5.4 indicating significant influence from the crustal contamination in this formation, whereas the ratio between Nb/La range from 0.4 to 1.3. These values indicate crustal contamination but not significant. The values between these elements suggest crustal influence on magma. The bivariate plot between Nb/Th vs Nb/La and Rb/La vs Th and Ce/Pb vs La/Nb also prepare to understand crustal contamination of the flows.

The value plotted in the Fig. 13 and 14 suggested that the samples of flows are not close to the mantle composition and precise near to the continental crust region and suggest significant some contamination from the upper crust. In the Fig. 15 La/Nb vs Ce/Pb samples of the study area falls into contaminated as well uncontaminated field.

Table 4.
Absolute abundances of Y and La-Lu in basalts (in ppm) of study area

Flow No.	³⁹ Y	⁵⁷ La	⁵⁵ Ce	⁵⁹ Pr	⁶⁰ Nd	⁶² Sm	⁶³ Eu	⁶⁴ Gd	⁶⁵ Tb	⁶⁶ Dy	⁶⁷ Ho	⁶⁸ Er	⁶⁹ Tm	⁷⁰ Yb	⁷¹ Lu	ΣY, La-Lu
F1	49.14	28.47	58.66	6.82	34.85	8.14	2.52	8.57	1.23	8.17	1.58	4.10	0.46	2.54	0.57	215.82
F2	52.12	21.25	47.18	5.88	31.72	7.88	2.54	8.55	1.27	8.62	1.69	4.34	0.49	2.73	0.60	196.86
F3	50.38	20.53	45.46	5.62	30.34	7.66	2.41	8.11	1.25	8.35	1.63	4.13	0.45	2.67	0.59	189.58
F4	36.39	10.65	25.23	3.37	19.01	5.31	1.81	5.65	0.89	6.06	1.21	3.00	0.34	1.90	0.42	121.24
F5	17.70	5.25	11.86	1.61	9.33	2.59	0.85	2.81	0.44	2.94	0.57	1.44	0.17	0.98	0.20	58.74
F6	50.26	19.95	38.70	4.42	2.94	5.35	1.73	6.43	1.06	7.50	1.59	4.39	0.51	3.03	0.67	167.73
F7	54.23	19.63	44.16	5.83	32.05	8.34	2.73	9.02	1.37	8.91	1.75	4.51	0.50	2.86	0.62	196.51

Conclusions

On the basis of various discriminatory diagram, this may be concluded that these basaltic rocks of the study area are tholeiitic in nature. Modified diagram of Simpson reveals that the basic Volcanic rocks of study area are very close to the Deccan trap and fall in the early stage basalt. Di-Ab-An triangular diagram as proposed by Kushiro (1972) indicates a concomitant increase in pyroxene as documented by the progression of the liquid line of descent in the system.

FeO+TiO₂-Al₂O₃-MgO diagram also confirms a high-iron rich tholeiitic character of the basaltic rocks. MgO-FeO-Al₂O₃ diagram after Pearce et al. (1977) which that the basaltic rocks of the present area belong to continental basalt tectonic environment. The calculated value of Mg# is

relatively low, which indicates that the basaltic rocks of the area have undergone relatively high degree of fractional crystallization, while low values of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/\text{CaO}$ ratio indicate the rocks of the area are alkali calcic in nature.

The higher concentration of chromium in the rocks of the study area is mainly due to the presence of pyroxene and iron enrichment, olivine, pyroxenes, amphiboles and titanomagnetites are the carriers of Co. The amount of Co shows a gradual change with differentiation in basaltic rocks. Higher concentration of Zn in the study area is due to the presence of Ferro magnesium minerals in greater proportion. Sr in the present rocks show a wide range from 105.39 ppm to 347.96 ppm. These values are agreeable with the values of tholeiitic basalts.

The low concentration of Nb and Ba suggests the tholeiitic nature of the basaltic rocks of the study area. Variation in Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y ratios of the basaltic lava flows of the area may be explained as low to moderate degree of partial melting of mantle, while the crustal assimilation can be explained by the variation of Zr and REE.

The average value of ΣY , La-Lu ≈ 163.69 in the basaltic lava flows of the study area is very close to the value as given by Frey et al. (1964) ΣY , La-Lu ≈ 147 for the tholeiitic basalts from continents.

In the area under investigation the extent of lava flows, total absence of pyroclastic accumulation and no indication of thickening of lava pile towards the particular centre and presence of dykes in the adjoining parts i.e., Narmada valley region, as discussed earlier, supports the fissure eruption type of vulcanocity.

On the basis of geochemical characteristics, it can be said that the nature of magma is of tholeiitic type. It is also suggested that through fissures the tholeiitic magma generated by partial melting of the mantle at lower temperature and hence may be related with the Deccan magmatism. Bivariate plot between Nb/La vs Nb/Th and Th vs Rb/La some samples of the lava flow close to the Enriched Mid-Ocean Ridge Basalt (E-MORB) and three samples are near to Lower Crust (LC) field. La/Nb vs Ce/Pb shows contaminated and some samples show uncontaminated field.

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